

DEFENSE SCIENCE IN CONTRIBUTING INDONESIA ECONOMIC GROWTH: INDONESIA 2045

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Abstract

Efforts for the defense of Indonesia are the responsibility of all Indonesian citizens. Welcoming Golden Indonesia 2045 as the goal of all Indonesians is inseparable from the geostrategic and geopolitical conditions of the world that can have an impact on Indonesia. The defense economy has a role in bridging the macro and micro-economy towards defense management, planning and deterrence, resource optimization, and defense force development policies. In addition, in guarding economic development that is influenced by culture and social and individual values, defense science is present to accompany economic development in a country. Cultural values derived from individual and social values of society will lead to economic growth, defense, and security of the country, especially in welcoming Indonesia 2045. They can be a challenge for the Indonesian government, especially in responding to changes in the values that exist in society. Faced with global conditions that might define the concept of state defense and security in the future. A country with a growing economy will be faced with external influences that may not favor growth. Therefore, economic development in Indonesia needs to be accompanied by the development of the concept of state defense and security based on national culture to avoid potential threats.

Keywords: Defense science, Economic Growth, Golden Indonesia 2045

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of philosophy by means of continual thinking fundamentally or radically to find the root of a problem or a reality can ultimately clarify reality itself. In line with that, defense also needs to pay attention to its philosophy which constantly questions the nature of various realities to know reality with certainty and clarity. In the end, all must be accompanied by a rational way of thinking by always thinking logically, systematically, and critically. Thus, this effort is the beginning of the development of branches of science, especially defense as a science. Based on the previous explanation, defense is also understood as a science. Van Peursen argues that in the past, science was part of philosophy so that the definition of science depended on the philosophical system adopted (Peursen, 1985).

Defense as science tends to generate scientific studies that can be used by humans in the defense sector. This relates to logic which is divided into formal logic and material logic or criticism (epistemology). Formal logic studies the principles or laws of thought that must be obeyed to think correctly and reach the truth. On the other hand, material logic or criticism (epistemology) looks at the content of knowledge and how this content can be accounted for; studying the sources and origins, the means, the process of occurrence, the possibilities, and the limits of science; truth and error; scientific method; and others.

Defense science in modern times as it is today is no longer a mere military domain. So many other scientific engagements are part of defense science. Community groups outside the military may still have difficulty understanding how the concept of defense as science is bound and related to all existing science at this time. To understand what and how defense science is, one needs to look at it from an epistemological perspective first. Defense as a science was born from various events in the past that gave birth to an origin and this developed into a strategy, increased into the science and art of war, which eventually became Defense Science and its relationships with other sciences (Supriyatno, 2014).

Defense science speaks in the scope and material of defense science itself. For instance, there are defense management, defense policy, defense cooperation, defense strategy, defense diplomacy, domestic defense, defense economics, defense strategy, defense intelligence, defense geography, defense values, and geopolitics, all of which are closely related to defense. Therefore, it can be understood that Defense as a philosophy of science is reflective thinking about the basic nature of the foundation of defense science which includes basic concepts, basic assumptions, preliminary principles, theoretical structures, and measures of scientific truth (The Liang Gie, 1978).

Furthermore, defense as science also includes defense as knowledge. These two things cannot be separated considering that defense is a systematic presentation of the nature of reality and determines the nature, source, and scope of knowledge. Tippe (2015) explains that knowledge is the entire thought, idea, and understanding that humans have about the world and everything in it, including humans and their lives. Knowledge and science have the same basic principles, which are two main sources, namely ideas and reality. Knowledge is obtained by reasoning so that it can be concluded, hence science is the result of rational reasoning from thinkers. Meanwhile, science is knowledge about both natural and social facts that apply in general and systematically. The purpose of science itself is to explain why an event occurs. It has empiric, systematic, objective, analytical, and verificative characteristics, especially in the field of defense itself.

In summary, defense as a concept of science and knowledge is an inseparable unit and supports one another. Defense science requires knowledge related to defense science itself in its implementation, considering that defense science contains multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary branches of science to support its studies to be more in-depth.

2. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Defense ontologically, epistemologically, and axiologically, also its position in the scientific family

Philosophy can have both general and specific uses in life. Its general use is the benefit that can be taken by people who study this philosophy in depth and can be in the form of facilitating critical problem-solving. The characteristic of using philosophy, in general, is that it is not attached to space and time. Meanwhile, its specific use can be in the form of solving specific problems in the limited dimensions of space and time.

Furthermore, philosophy can then be grouped into defense philosophy, which is closely related to ideological philosophy and military philosophy. In discussing defense, understanding the philosophy of defense and security is very important. Eppler (2009) states that defense is the spearhead in understanding a country. This is because defense is a reality that determines the sovereignty and safety of a nation and state. Defense itself has become the main national need since the country's sovereignty has been recognized. In ideological philosophy, Pancasila becomes the basis for thinking in everyday life. In this regard, ideological philosophy can be considered as a basic foundation in living a state life in Indonesia, Pancasila as the ideology of the nation and state. In the scope of military philosophy related to the involvement of military personnel, the TNI, in particular, can refer to Barry Buzan's opinion that divides the security sector into five fields: military, political, environmental, economic, and social. This means that the military approach is only one of them in the national security system. The role of the military focuses on the capabilities of defense institutions, threat assessment, and the like. Socio-cultural and religious relations are needed to understand the dynamics of threats and the interaction of security factors.

Figure 1: The overlap between Defense, Ideological, and Military Philosophy

Source: designed by the authors (2022)

From Figure 1 above, it can be concluded that the philosophy of defense, ideology, and military has a relationship studied from the ontological, epistemological, and axiological relations of the three to respond to the existing threats. According to Tippe (2019), **ontologically**, defense will discuss the object of defense science itself, which is a reflection of the behavior of a state to maintain and develop a sustainable state. The object is essentially state behavior which is defined as guarding the existence of the state against many threats, both by individuals and by the state, through defense and security mechanisms. One example of these threats is separatism by the Free Papua Movement OPM (Indonesian: Organisasi Papua Merdeka, OPM) in Papua. The National Liberation Army of West Papua-OPM separatism is a threat to the Republic of Indonesia in relation to the sustainability of the country. In state behavior, this is related to social needs that are contrary to the purpose of the existence of a country. Multi-disciplinary defense views this separatist group from a political perspective (foreign political interests to divide the Republic of Indonesia and primordialism to separate themselves based on a history of identity that is different from the Indonesian nation), economic perspective (where infrastructure development and other facilities have been implemented by the President Jokowi in the last 5 years is deemed adequate), and law and governance perspective (where government policies and law enforcement in Papua are facing obstacles in their implementation). Additionally, from an educational perspective, their level of education is also deemed insufficient for rational, healthy, and tolerant thinking for social welfare and acceptance of Pancasila as the state ideology. Meanwhile, state behavior requires individuals, organizations, and government officials to base their behaviors on Pancasila values, especially in determining state defense mechanisms that are oriented towards Indonesia's national interests.

Epistemologically, the concept of defense can be obtained through qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods through a critical thinking system approach to solve problems faced by the Indonesian state and nation. The existing approaches come from a multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary side. This means that defense, military, and Pancasila are integrated with studies that come from various types of science that discuss everything holistically and sustainably. For example, the separatist group of the National Liberation Army of West Papua-OPM does not adhere to this ideology because they think they are not good Indonesian citizens and want to become independent or be separated from Indonesia. It is known that the political and economic justice felt by the region is one of the causes of separatism. However, the Papua case is not only due to dissatisfaction, but also other, more fundamental problems, which are ideology and foreign interest. In principle, separatism must be eliminated completely in the sense that there is no longer any desire to be independent. In this context, the emphasis is more on the psychological aspects as well as the philosophy of guerrilla warfare "to win people's hearts and minds". Separatism must have a multi-faceted background concerning ideology, politics, economy, and culture, while the issue of defense and security are mere reverberation.

Axiologically, defense is supported by ideology and the military has certainly provided benefits and contributions to the existing state, both in terms of the contribution of a national defense and security policy related to the existence of the state in building harmonious, dynamic, and peaceful relations between countries. For Indonesia, strong defense and security indicate that

Indonesia is a country that runs systematically, and its existence should be taken into account. In addressing OPM in Papua, there are several short-term steps that the central government should take. First, enforcing the law on racist actions against the Papuan people, including those committed against Papuan students in Surabaya some time ago. Second, taking firm steps to arrest and punish the intellectual actors who created the riots in Papua who are suspected of coming from groups of “political heartache” and groups of foreign interest networks. Third, holding an equal-participatory dialogue between the central government and Papuan community leaders and representatives. Fourth, committing and applying human rights enforcement programs and protecting the basic social rights of the Papuan people. Fifth, reducing the tension of militarism policy in handling Papua because militarism will only result in armed resistance that is more militant than the existing groups.

The position of defense in science is stated in the Decree of the Minister of Research, Technology and Higher Education of the Republic of Indonesia No. 257/M/Kpt/2017 concerning the Name of Study Program in Higher Education. In the ministerial decree, defense is included in the science branch of the Social Sciences family. This indicates that defense is a social science that specifically addresses peace and conflict resolution, diplomacy, economics, energy security, maritime security, management, asymmetric warfare, and strategies in land, sea, and air defense. All these branches of knowledge are important in supporting the development of defense science in Indonesia. Based on this explanation, defense science can be understood as the study of how to manage national resources and strength during times of peace, war, and post-war, to face military and non-military threats to territorial integrity, state sovereignty, and the safety of the entire nation to realize national security.

In line with the previous explanation, the Rector of the Defense University, Lt. Gen. TNI Dr. Tri Legionosuko, S.IP., M.A.P (Media Indonesia, 2019) also argues that the dynamics of the development of a strategic environment that presents the complexity of future threats prompted the government to establish the Defense University, which studies defense science clusters. The outcome to be achieved is intellectual cadres of state defense who become think tanks in formulating and perfecting a national defense system that is adaptable, flexible, and reliable. Considering that defense is not an independent science, defense has a very close relationship with various other sciences, such as philosophy, politics, anthropology, demography, economics, history, law, state science, earth science, exact science, language, and psychology. Thus, defense science is a branch of social science that needs more attention to create a strong national defense and security.

2.2 The Concept of Indonesia Defense in the Regions based on Geopolitical and Geoeconomic Developments

Indonesia’s national defense efforts are the responsibility of all Indonesian citizens. In other words, national defense is not only the responsibility of the TNI and POLRI, but civil society is also very responsible for state defense and security. The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia also illustrates that national defense and security efforts are carried out by using the total defense and security system of the people, or total defense (Silvester, 2018). The total defense is essentially all efforts to maintain the defense and security of the state, which includes

all the people and all national resources, national facilities and infrastructure, as well as the entire territory of the country as a whole and comprehensive defense unit. In other words, the implementation of the total unit is based on the awareness of the rights and obligations of all citizens and the belief in their strength to maintain the survival of the Indonesian nation and state that is independent, united, sovereign, just, and prosperous.

There are several features of the total defense, namely:

- 1) Democracy, namely the orientation of state defense and security which is served by and for the benefit of all people.
- 2) Universality, namely all national resources are utilized for defense efforts.
- 3) Territorial, namely the title of defense force is spread throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, following its archipelagic geographical condition.

The national defense and security system developed by the Indonesian nation is in accordance with the conditions of the Indonesian nation. The location of Indonesia's territory, which is in the crossing point (between two continents and two) has its advantages but also involves major security threats, such as military threats from other countries and international crimes. In addition, Indonesia's archipelagic condition requires a strong defense and security system to avoid the threat of division. With such conditions, it can be concluded that the total defense is the best system for the Indonesian people in facing threats.

Defense Minister Prabowo feels the need to increase the defense budget to balance the existing geopolitical and geo-economic situation (Bayu, 2019). According to him, this budget is needed to streamline spending on the main weaponry system (Indonesian: Alat Utama Sistem Persenjataan, Alutsista) such as radar. Apart from spending on the radar, Prabowo assesses the need to modernize defense equipment, such as ships and aircraft, and strengthen cyber defense in Indonesia. Strengthening cyber defense is considered important because currently many digital startups have sprung up in Indonesia. These startups are all connected to big data on the internet, so it is deemed necessary to anticipate so that cyber data is not used for the benefit of other countries.

Apart from that, national defense is also related to the facilities and infrastructure for securing borders, outer islands, and vulnerable areas. To that end, the TNI Commander also added a program to continue building TNI forces on Natuna Island and Yamdena/Selaru Island, continuing the construction of standby force barracks and Sarpras Koopssus TNI and carrying out the construction of Sarpras Kogabwilhan I, II, and III. In addition, the rivalry between China and the United States in the geopolitical and geoeconomic sectors (trade war) is one of the modern and real examples of current instability (Astungkoro, 2019). Increasing China's power as a new superpower with the Belt Road Initiative concept is one example of China's power in controlling world trade. Amid these developments, the Indo-Pacific emerged as a new global center of gravity by developing as a barometer and forming a meaningful new order for the world community. Moreover, France is also currently starting to increase its security

partners and Russia is also strengthening itself by formulating hybrid and cyber warfare strategies.

The latest condition, namely the polemic of the entry of ships from China into Natuna waters in the Riau Islands, is attracting public attention. Moreover, the vessels are suspected of frequently stealing fish, even though several monitoring vessels have been deployed to Natuna waters. Rather than taking firm action against ships from China, President Joko Widodo (Jokowi) seems to have prioritized peaceful diplomatic routes to China (CNN Indonesia, 2020). Even so, the President stressed that he would not compromise when defending Indonesia's sovereignty. The East Natuna gas field has been known for its potential since 1973; nearly 45 years ago. Its estimated content is around 46 billion cubic feet, which is the largest gas block in the world that has not been explored (untapped gas). One of the ways to improve defense and strengthen deterrents in Natuna with the limited Indonesian state budget is to collaborate in gas operations with companies from countries with strong military forces. The country will not allow the operations of its oil and gas companies to be disrupted and will establish military cooperation with Indonesia.

In addition, the relationship between Iran and the United States (US) is getting increasingly precarious, even there has been a fierce war. According to CNBC International, the US reportedly shot dead top brass of Iran's military forces. The escalation marks the increasingly divided US-Iran relations. The escalating geopolitical tensions between the US and Iran have fueled fears that a third world war will soon erupt. However, the wave of protests was also staged by many Americans who did not want war, considering that war only costs a lot of money, takes lives, and causes suffering. Reflecting on this incident, global economic growth in 2019 is estimated at 3.2 percent, while in 2020, it is projected to increase slightly to 3.5 percent. About 90 percent of countries are experiencing a slowdown in economic growth marked by trade wars between developed countries, such as China and America, as something that is worsening the situation. To anticipate this, good collaboration between the government and business actors is needed in strengthening the Indonesian economy (Hasibuan, 2020).

Responding to the existing dynamics, as a result of increasingly dynamic geopolitics and geoeconomics, several things need to be considered in the Indonesian defense system. Siahaan (2019) argues that several strategic matters need to be resolved by the new Minister of Defense. One of them is the constitutional basis of the people's universal defense and security (Indonesian: *Pertahanan Keamanan Rakyat Semesta, Hankamrata*). The reform era of the "party" of democracy has resulted in various statutory provisions in the field of defense and security that have come from the body of the 1945 Constitution, which contains articles that are prone to distortion of the basic values / philosophies contained in its preamble. On the other hand, the basic and main defense doctrine is developed and elaborated by the TNI based on the values that underlie the national identity contained in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution. As a result, the space for the TNI in implementing defense and security will always be constrained by various statutory provisions, which are compiled based on values that are incompatible with the national identity, especially those that lead to liberal democracy, individualism, and capitalism.

The logical basis for understanding the security system is a comprehensive perception that the system of life as a nation includes various fundamental and existential dimensions, such as ideology, economy, politics, social, culture, and defense and security. Because they are interrelated and cannot be mutually exclusive, but instead are mutually complementary and interdependent, the development of these dimensions must be maximized to achieve optimal results with the principle of “mutual support and strengthening”. Political and economic development, for example, can run well when the national defense and security situation is positive-conducive. On the other hand, the construction of the National Security System is impossible without the support of other dimensions.

The National Security System, like other national life systems (politics, economy, etc.), is built and driven to support development efforts or national transformation towards achieving national goals/objectives. To achieve these national goals, many aspects must be protected, safeguarded, and implemented, including various national interests. For Indonesia, building an ideal power is still nearly impossible due to budget constraints. It is impossible to build an alliance to build a defense pact because of the principle of a free and active foreign policy. Therefore, the only logical, realistic choice is total defense.

Another challenge is in terms of borders. During the last five years, conditions at national borders have raised various cases of disputes with other countries, economic and humanity crimes, and other negative excesses due to weak border management. The rampant smuggling of various products and commodities to the number of illegal immigrants who have made this country their basis for action is an indication of how negligent the government has been in maintaining and managing the homeland of Nusantara. The condition is increasingly crucial in connection with the potential conflict in the South China Sea involving several major countries. Although this conflict did not involve Indonesia directly, this country could be affected. The Defense Ministry’s purchase of Black Hawk assault helicopters some time ago is the right solution for managing and securing national borders.

An integrated defense system between national defense partners is needed. This system has become increasingly important since the United States government formulated the doctrine of preemptive self defense or commonly known as anticipatory self defense. In this context, the defense organization of a country must have a strong backbone so that it can perform excellent penetration and communication along national borders. Defense issues must be handled with the latest solutions that optimize technology towards an integrated digitalized battlefield. In addition, the problem of the threat of national disintegration and radicalism is the next homework that must be anticipated and get the attention of the government, aside from geopolitical and geo-economic turmoil.

2.3 Defense Science and Defense Economics

Global developments that have increasingly reduced boundaries between countries have created new challenges that require a country to be active in fighting for economic growth as one of the pillars of national defense to survive global competition. Existing political turmoil, such as what happened to Nigeria some time ago, has also caused crude oil prices to rise and

affected the economies of other countries due to the increase in fuel prices. The defense economy itself is expected to create a powerful national economic strategy as a means of defense from turmoil in other countries.

In line with the above, the Deputy Chairman of the Indonesian Chamber of Commerce and Industry for Investment and Transportation, Chris Kanter, states that the economy is a national defense force. He also adds that there are three things in the economy that are closely related to defense, namely food security, energy security, and financial security. The three elements of strength can build a strong national economy to support national defense (Kompas, 2010).

Furthermore, defense policy is entering a period of changing momentum which requires proper economic analysis if resources are to be allocated efficiently between objectives in both the defense and civilian sectors. The Defense Economy applies economic tools to defense studies, arms restriction, conversion, and peace. Apart from that, Defense Economy is also a sub-sector of the economy that connects economic methods with a special topic, namely the defense sector. As an area of study, defense economics covers topics and aspects that exist from peace science and conflict studies. Defense economics also focuses on understanding the dynamics of military spending, conflict, and the related economic aspects of the defense sector. Understanding these dynamics will help increase control of gun restrictions and conflict instability, thereby contributing to human survival and future violence (Saddler, et. Al, 1995). So, it can be concluded that defense economy is a science that studies the dynamics of defense spending and related economic aspects as a result of the dynamics of these expenditures to achieve efficiency and effectiveness in allocating resources owned by a country so that it can contribute to the sustainability of human civilization in the future.

In addition, economic development is one of the development goals that represent the welfare of the community. This economic perspective tends to dominate the way of thinking about the definition of development and welfare. In fact, economic development is also a cultural process because the economy itself is part of a cultural reality that can form an economic sense (McPherson in Chavoshbashi, Ghadami, Broumand, & Marzban, 2012, 7800). Thus, it is not surprising that regional development in Indonesia can nurture a culture of consumerism for its people when urban economic development focuses more on this cultural reality. However, many “good” cultures have a significant impact on economic development. The role of culture in the economy is currently receiving major attention from economists and it is believed that the economic culture of a region is a useful tool for development (Guiso, Sapienza, & Zingales, 2006, 45).

Figure 2: The concept of Defense Economy

Source: Yusgiantoro (2019)

Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that the role of the defense economy is to bridge the macro, micro, and quantitative economies towards defense management, planning and deterrence, resource optimization, and defense force development policies. In addition, in guarding economic development which is influenced by culture and social and individual values, defense science is also present to accompany economic development in a country. This will be related to geopolitical and geostrategic conditions in regional countries and within Indonesia. The rapid economic growth and the accompanying cultural influences will certainly present a threat to the Indonesian nation. Therefore, multidisciplinary defense science will offer solutions that can be used to deal with problems that threaten the existence of the state.

Welcoming Golden Indonesia 2045 as the goal of all Indonesians is inseparable from the geostrategic and geopolitical conditions of the world that can have an impact on Indonesia. Geopolitical conditions show that Indonesia has a huge potential to become the Golden Indonesia, which is being brave and sovereign, but many things need to be addressed before it can be achieved (Ericssen, 2019). Geopolitics is understood as an analytical framework that shows the relationship between foreign and domestic policies that seeks to understand, predict, and explain international political behavior in geographic variables, in this case, the Indonesian state. Therefore, in the context of moving towards a Golden Indonesia 2045, many things must be prepared, especially in the face of domestic and foreign geopolitical conditions.

To address this, there is also a relationship between the evolution of the political situation between countries and the geopolitical evolution of the world. Globalization, border issues, trade in goods, and financial flows have an impact on many countries. A world that was once bipolar with competition between America and the Soviet Union, was dominated by two geopolitical and economic blocs. However, at present, world conditions are becoming more complex with the power of the third country of China, which is starting to dominate the world

economy. With this in mind, Indonesia must put itself in the best position to compete in this developing world constellation.

The authors believe that law enforcement and justice will play a crucial role in achieving the Golden Indonesia 2045 or one hundred years of Indonesia's age. Law and justice serve as the foundation of Indonesian nationalism, so without serious law enforcement, citizens' loyalty to the republic can diminish over time. Future bureaucratic services must be based on government principles that smile at the people. If law enforcement does not go well, there will be disorder through the process of disorientation of the law, distrust, disobedience, and disintegration of the nation. The internal condition of the nation and state must be prioritized to strengthen the driving force in the international arena.

Apart from the realm of law enforcement and justice, several things must be addressed in welcoming the Golden Indonesia 2045. The first is to strengthen unity in diversity by strengthening pluralism, tolerance, and democracy. Second, to fight against radicalism and movements that threaten the integrity of Indonesia's ideology and territory. Last but not least is to address social and economic disparities so that they are not used as a trigger and incendiary tool for radicalism. Ideologies that are contrary to Pancasila can also be a threat to Golden Indonesia 2045. It must be understood that Pancasila includes all the supporting elements for the realization of national welfare, namely upholding justice, respecting human rights, building the people's economy.

Figure 3: Conceptualization Model of Cultural Value and Economic Growth to National Defense and Security

Source: Processed and adapted by the authors from Asmin (2018)

Based on Figure 3, it can be understood that cultural values derived from individual and social values of society will lead to economic growth, which will also lead to the defense and security of a country, especially in welcoming Indonesia 2045. This can be interpreted as a challenge for the Indonesian government in responding to changes in the values that exist in society in the face of global conditions that might define the concept of state defense and security in the future. A country with a growing economy will be faced with outside influences who may not like the progress that is being made. Therefore, in line with economic development in Indonesia, the concept of state defense and security based on national culture needs to be developed to ward off potential threats.

3. CONCLUSION

In the future, Indonesia will continue to face a multipolar geopolitical environment, and Asia, which will become the world's economic center with the largest middle class, can continue to develop rapidly. By the middle of this century, the world economy will be twice as large as it is now and its growth will be faster than that of the world population, which is estimated to reach 9.8 billion people by 2045. Shared Economy and a cashless society will become more common, especially because modernization, including connectivity, is increasingly spreading to various developing countries. With all these opportunities, Indonesia must continue to be aware of various risks and need to anticipate the financial and economic crisis in the next three decades in which inequality will continue to be a world trend. Similarly, Indonesia needs to anticipate geostrategic competition that includes military development and militarization of conflict areas that will continue to unfold. In addition, the Indonesian nation also needs to anticipate the outbreak of a major war internationally considering radicalism, extremism, and terrorism that will continue to haunt the world, not to mention the threat of pandemics and endemics from infectious diseases.

In 2045, the total population of Indonesia is estimated to reach 321 million people, with a productive age population of around 209 million. Therefore, Indonesia's economy is projected to be worth \$ 9 trillion and will automatically be included in the top five world economies. More than 70% of Indonesia's population will live in urban areas considering that regional growth centers will multiply, especially due to more equitable infrastructure development. Indonesia's development must continue to adapt to the times and changing conditions of the people. Development in Indonesia must increasingly prioritize ethics and care for marginalized groups. In the 21st century, Indonesia must carry out its development by prioritizing our nation's Indonesian identity. Therefore, the youth must be determined to preserve the local culture and language so that they do not become extinct. Anticipating the growing development of artificial intelligence and automation, the Indonesian nation must also continue to keep the Indonesian people as the main implementers in the country's development strategy going forward. The government must also ensure that the development that is carried out can not only provide material prosperity but can also provide welfare for the Indonesian people. Development, in this case, should not only emphasize the aspects of equality but also equal opportunity. Indonesia's future development must also be more based on local wisdom and

meet regional needs to create new economic growth centers that can bridge regional disparities that have so far characterized the Indonesian economy.

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